

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

List of Target Organizations / Stakeholders

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Change log

Version ¹	Date	Amended by	Changes
1.0	30-11-2016	Rangajeewa Ratnayake	
1.1	04-12-2016	Massimiliano Cannata	Included minor corrections and removed personal data

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
1.0	UOM	Rangajeewa Ratnayake Prasad Dhananjaya Bandara
1.1	SUPSI	Massimiliano cannata

NOTES:

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For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

This document contains the list of target organizations and the information about the stakeholders who participated for the first policy workshop which held on 21st of November 2016. The document also contains stakeholders' views about the 4onse project.

1 Introduction

The research project on 4 times open & non-conventional technology for sensing the environment (4onse) is focused on setting up a fully accessible, royalty free and low cost climate monitoring system based on open hardware, software and standards. The project case study area, where the 4onse system will be deployed and investigated is the Deduru Oya basin (Figure 1), which is the fourth largest river basin in Sri Lanka. At present, this area suffers from issues like floods and droughts. Disaster warning is truly a challenging task in this area, due to absence of real time, dense and continuous meteorological data.

The project includes three policy workshops to raise further awareness about the project among stakeholders. The aim of this initiative is direct distribution and presentation of the 4onse system and results amongst the stakeholders. Other four scientific work-shops will be held in opportune locations to disseminate the 4onse approach among scientists. A final conference validating project outcomes with stakeholders and wider community is foreseen. The first policy workshop of the project was held on 21st of November 2016 at hotel Ozo, Colombo, Sri Lanka. The main objectives of the workshop are:

- To aware the stakeholders about the 4onse project
- To promote stakeholders on using open source climate monitoring systems for managing natural disasters
- To identify the specific needs and priorities of having fully accessible, royalty free and low cost climate monitoring system for Deduru Oya basin
 - To identify the essential climate variables to be included in the system

Figure 1 - Deduru oya river basin, case study area of the project.

2 List of target organizations / stakeholders

2.1 List of target organizations

1. Irrigation Department, Colombo
2. Irrigation Department, Kurunegala
3. International Water Management Institute (IWMI)
4. National Building Research Organization (NBRO)
5. Climate Resilient Improvement Project, Irrigation Department, Colombo
6. Central Environmental Authority (CEA)
7. Mahaweli Development Authority
8. Sri Lanka Telecom
9. Lanka Rain Water Harvesting Forum (LRWHF)
10. Disaster Management Centre (DMC)
11. Rice research and development institute, Bathalegoda

2.2 Details of Stakeholders

Name	Organization	Designation
S. Mohanarajah	Irrigation Department	Director of Irrigation (Water management & training)
S.M.M.R.K. Saurakoon	Irrigation Department	Chief Engineer
H.G.M. Kulasinghe	Irrigation Department	
Tim Hannan	Climate Resilient Improvement Project, Irrigation Department	Team Leader
Medhani Jayakodi	Climate Resilient Improvement Project, Irrigation Department	Chief Engineer
Dr. (Ms) Soumya Balasubramanya	International Water Management Institute	Research Environmental Economist
Nishadi Eriyagama	International Water Management Institute	Water Resource Engineer
W. K. Chathuranga Kumarasiri	National Building Research Organization	Scientist
W.G.W. Gnanatheepan	National Building Research Organization	Scientist
C.H. Edussunya	Central Environmental Authority	Assistant Director
K.P.S. Uthpala	Central Environmental Authority	Environmental officer
S.V.P. Gunasekara	Mahaweli Development Authority	Engineer
K.K. Gunawardana	Telecom	Deputy Director General
Ama Rajakarunanayaka	Lanka Rain Water Harvesting Forum	Deputy Director
A.P. Benthota	Rice research and development institute,	Director

Bathalegoda

3 Stakeholders' views about the 4nse project

In general the feedback received from the stakeholder is very positive. All of the actors declared their interest in the project as a mean of accessing dense climatic data (in time and space) that would be beneficiary for addressing a number of issues like for example: better manage the water resource to cope with water conflicts (energy, irrigation and flooding) and advance in scientific studies on crop production/desieses for food security.

The following bulleted list shows some of the important specific views made by the stakeholders at the first policy workshop:

- Stakeholders highlighted the importance of considering the evapotranspiration and rainfall issues in the case study area when deciding the system parameters.
- It was discussed at the workshop to looking at the institutional & policy aspects, barriers and opportunities when implementing the proposed weather station project.
- IWMI has informed that they have already initiated a similar kind of project while taking different aspects of the system into one platform.
- It was discussed about the limitations such as inconsistency of analysis, conventional data collection methods, and non-standardization of data produced by the Meteorological Department. Further, the stakeholders highlighted the importance of involving the Meteorological Department in this project.
- IWMI and LRWHF shared their experience on problems they faced in implementing similar kind of weather station projects in rural areas of Sri Lanka. They highlighted the importance of selecting proper energy source for the proposed weather station system, capacity of the batteries which are going to use for the system and protecting the system from human and animal threats such as bird nests, spider webs, etc.
- Stakeholders of Rice research and development institute highlighted the importance of proposed climate monitoring system in crop management of Sri Lanka
- Further, it was discussed about the network coverage of the basin area and solving the issues related to network regulators.
- Stakeholders also made their views on developing proper data sharing mechanism, which is not currently practiced in Sri Lanka.

Appendix A Some captured moments at the workshop

Prof P.K.S. Mahanama, Senior Lecturer, Department of Town & Country Planning and team leader of University of Moratuwa, welcoming the participants

Deputy Vice Chancellor, Prof R.A. Attalage addressing the gathering

Prof M. Cannata, Professor in Geomatics of University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland and project manager of the 4nse project, introducing the project to the stakeholders and sharing his experience in similar research projects implemented in Switzerland.

Panelists at the Head Table: Left to Right – Dr R. Rathnayake (Project Coordinator & Head, Department of Town & Country Planning, UoM), Prof M. Cannata (Project Manager & Professor in Geomatics, SUPSI), Prof P.K.S. Mahanama (Team Leader & Senior Lecturer, Department of Town & Country Planning, UoM), Dr M.F.M. Firdhous (Senior Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, UoM), Eng P.M. Karunarathna (Dean, Faculty of Information Technology, UoM), Mr S. Mohanarajah (Director of Irrigation, Irrigation Department of Sri Lanka), Mr B.H. Sudantha (Senior Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, UoM)

Stakeholders making thier views

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